

The Utility of Diagnostic Scores: A Comparison of Diagnostic Classification Models and IRT-Based Methods for Subscore Reporting

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ABSTRACT

Despite the increasing demand for diagnostic information, observed subscores have been often reported to lack adequate psychometric qualities such as reliability, distinctiveness, and validity. Therefore, several statistical techniques based on CTT and IRT frameworks have been proposed to improve the quality of subscores. More recently, DCM has also attracted increasing attention as a powerful diagnostic tool that can provide fine-tuned diagnostic feedback. Despite its potential, there has been a dearth of research evaluating the psychometric quality of DCM, especially in comparison with diagnostic methods from other psychometric frameworks. Therefore, in this simulation study, DCM was compared with two IRT-based subscore estimation methods in terms of classification accuracy, distinctiveness, and incremental criterion-related validity evidence of subscores. Manipulated factors included diagnostic methods, subscale length, item difficulty distribution, intercorrelations of subscores, and criterion validity coefficients. For classification accuracy, all diagnostic methods yielded comparable results when the center of item difficulty coincided with mean examinee ability and cut-scores. However, when average item difficulty was mismatched with mean examinee ability and cut-scores, DCM yielded substantially higher/lower classification accuracy than IRT-based methods with direction and magnitude of discrepancy depending on the type of agreement measures employed. For subscore distinctiveness, compared to IRT-based methods, DCM yielded subscores more distinct from each other and overall scores when continuous rather than discrete subscores were utilized. Lastly, regarding incremental criterion-related validity evidence, the contribution of DCM estimates over and above overall scores tended to be comparable to but slightly smaller than that of IRT-based methods. Additionally, higher classification accuracy was associated with longer subscales, item difficulty distribution more aligned with examinee ability distribution and cut-scores, and higher intercorrelations of subscores. The same conditions except for higher intercorrelations of subscores also tended to be associated with higher subscore distinctiveness. In contrast, incremental criterion-related validity evidence of subscores was largely a function of intercorrelations of subscores and magnitude of criterion validity coefficients: it increased with lower intercorrelations of subscores and higher criterion validity coefficients. In general, the results of this study suggested that IRT-based methods would be preferable over DCM as diagnostic means when item responses are obtained from IRT-based assessment forms.

INTRODUCTION

Educational stakeholders have become increasingly interested in obtaining scores on the subscales for diagnostic purposes (Brennan, 2012; Sinharay et al., 2011). Students want to get detailed information about their strengths and weaknesses to remediate the latter. Similarly, teachers want to utilize such information for making placement decisions and providing instruction customized to the student's individual needs (Firestone, 2014; Haladyna & Kramer, 2004; Kunnan & Jang, 2009). Despite their potential to provide diagnostic information, as with the total score, subscores must meet professional quality standards before being reported to stakeholders (Haberman, 2008; Tate, 2004). This is in line with Standards 1.14 and 2.3 of the Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing (American Educational Research Association [AERA], American Psychological Association [APA], & National

Council on Measurement in Education [NCME], 2014) which require that each reported score must provide sufficient evidence of reliability, distinctiveness, and validity for the intended purposes.

Evaluating the Utility of Subscores

Subscore reliability is especially important when the primary goal of the test is to provide diagnostic information (Feinberg & Wainer, 2014). The required level of reliability depends on the intended use of the scores (Sinharay et al., 2019). Reliability coefficients of .80 or higher are generally recommended for diagnostic or remedial decisions (Nunally, 1978; Sinharay et al., 2019), whereas .70 or higher is in general required for test scores (Choi & Papageorgiou, 2020). In practice, however, subscores frequently exhibit lower reliability than total scores because they are based on fewer items. Some testing programs report subscores from as few as five items (Goodman & Hambleton, 2004), although simulation studies suggest that approximately 20 items per subscale may be needed to achieve acceptable reliability (Sinharay, 2010). Operational constraints such as testing time, examinee fatigue, and item development costs often limit subscale length and, consequently, subscore reliability (Sinharay et al., 2019).

Beyond reliability, useful subscores should provide information that is distinct from the overall score and from other subscores. Distinctiveness reflects the extent to which a subscore captures unique aspects of performance. However, substantial correlations among subscores are common, largely because many educational assessments use a retrofitting approach in which subscores are derived from tests originally designed to measure a largely unidimensional construct rather than to provide diagnostic information (Haberman, 2008; Luecht et al., 2006; Sinharay et al., 2019).

Closely related to distinctiveness is incremental validity, or added value, which refers to the extent to which subscores provide information beyond that conveyed by the total score (Haberman, 2008). Researchers have argued that subscores are most likely to demonstrate added value when they are both highly reliable and sufficiently distinct from the remainder of the test (Haberman, 2008; Haberman et al., 2009; Puhon et al., 2010; Sinharay, 2010). Thus, subscores contribute meaningful information beyond the total score only when they measure unique aspects of performance with adequate precision and stability (Choi & Papageorgiou, 2020).

Several methods have been proposed to evaluate the utility of subscores. Haberman's (2008) proportional reduction in mean squared error (PRMSE) framework evaluates whether observed subscores predict true subscores more accurately than the total score. Bulut et al. (2016) proposed a profile-reliability approach that separates between-person and within-person reliability, providing information about both overall score precision and the distinctiveness of score profiles. In addition, Davison et al. (2015) examined the incremental contribution of subscores to the prediction of external criteria. Although these methods differ in their operational definitions, they collectively emphasize that useful subscores must demonstrate both adequate reliability and meaningful differentiation from the total score.

IRT-Based Approaches to Improving Subscores

Because subscores often lack sufficient reliability and distinctiveness to provide meaningful added value beyond the total score, several statistical techniques to improve the psychometric quality of subscores have been proposed from classical test theory (CTT) and item response theory (IRT) frameworks. The common thread running through these methods is that they utilize collateral or ancillary information to improve the subscore estimation (de la Torre, 2008; de la Torre & Patz, 2005; Haberman, 2008; Haberman & Sinharay, 2010; Kahraman & Kamata, 2004; Wainer et al., 2001; Wang et al., 2004; Yao & Boughton, 2007; Yen, 1987). The ancillary information typically involved in these methods is the examinee's performances on items outside the target subscale (i.e., out-of-scale items). This type of information is considered in-test collateral information because it is inherent in the test and can be obtained with the examinees' item responses. In contrast, out-of-test collateral information includes demographic variables

(e.g., sex, age, and race) and education variables (e.g., grade level and courses taken) that are not contained in item responses but provide additional information about examinee characteristics (de la Torre et al., 2011).

Among the approaches developed to improve subscore estimation, augmentation-based item response theory (AIRT) and multidimensional item response theory (MIRT) have received considerable attention. Despite their similar goals and often comparable performance, the two approaches differ conceptually. AIRT improves subscore estimates through a post hoc augmentation process that incorporates ancillary information derived from examinees' performance on other subdomains. In contrast, MIRT improves estimation by directly modeling the multidimensional structure of the assessment and incorporating correlations among latent traits to estimate all latent traits simultaneously. Consequently, MIRT is often considered theoretically more appealing and more flexible in accommodating complex test structures. However, these advantages come at the cost of greater computational demands and larger sample-size requirements for accurate and stable parameter estimation.

Although both approaches can reduce estimation error and improve score precision (de la Torre et al., 2011; de la Torre & Patz, 2005; Haberman & Sinharay, 2010; Yao & Boughton, 2007), enhanced subscores are not necessarily more useful. Because both AIRT and MIRT borrow information from related dimensions, gains in reliability are often accompanied by increased correlations among subscores. Researchers have repeatedly documented this trade-off between reliability and distinctiveness (Feinberg & Wainer, 2014; Stone et al., 2010). Therefore, improvements in reliability do not automatically translate into greater incremental validity. The practical value of enhanced subscores depends on whether the increase in reliability outweighs the accompanying reduction in distinctiveness.

Diagnostic Classification Models

The increasing demand for diagnostic information has led to growing interest in diagnostic classification models (DCMs). Unlike CTT and IRT approaches, which assume continuous latent traits, DCMs assume discrete latent attributes and classify examinees into mastery and nonmastery categories for each latent trait, also called skill or attribute. Attribute mastery is determined by the posterior probability of mastery (PPM; also known as the marginal probability of attribute mastery). Specifically, examinees with a PPM of .50 or higher are classified as masters, whereas those with a PPM below .50 are classified as nonmasters (Rupp et al., 2010). Accordingly, DCMs provide detailed diagnostic feedback (i.e., an attribute profile) regarding specific skills or knowledge components rather than overall proficiency.

DCMs possess several characteristics that make them attractive for diagnostic assessment. First, they provide fine-grained information regarding examinees' strengths and weaknesses at the attribute level. Second, they explicitly incorporate substantive theories of cognition through the specification of a Q-matrix that links items to underlying attributes. Third, DCMs can accommodate complex multidimensional structures and attribute hierarchies that often characterize learning and cognitive processes (Rupp et al., 2010; de la Torre & Minchen, 2014).

Because DCMs focus on classification rather than continuous score estimation, their reliability is typically evaluated using classification accuracy and classification consistency. Researchers have shown that the quality of DCM classifications depends on several factors, including the number of items measuring each attribute, the quality of the Q-matrix, the complexity of the underlying model, and the correlations among attributes (Rupp et al., 2010; Templin & Bradshaw, 2013). Under favorable conditions, DCMs can achieve high levels of classification accuracy while providing detailed diagnostic information.

Another potential advantage of DCMs is that they may alleviate some of the trade-offs observed in traditional subscore estimation. Because DCMs classify examinees into discrete mastery categories rather than estimating continuous proficiency scores, they may produce more distinct diagnostic information while maintaining acceptable levels of reliability. Furthermore, DCMs often require fewer assumptions regarding the dimensional structure of test scores than traditional subscore approaches.

Despite their promise, researchers have argued that the complexity involved in estimating and interpreting DCMs warrants clear justification for their use over simpler approaches grounded in CTT or IRT (Montero et al., 2003; Sinharay & Haberman, 2009; Wilhelm & Robitzsch, 2009). However, relatively little research has examined the psychometric quality of DCM estimates in comparison with subscores derived from IRT-based approaches. Existing research has largely focused on classification accuracy, model fit, and attribute recovery within the DCM framework. In contrast, far less attention has been devoted to evaluating whether DCM estimates provide information that is distinct from overall proficiency and whether they offer incremental validity beyond simpler measurement approaches. Consequently, the relative strengths and limitations of DCMs, AIRT, and MIRT with respect to the utility of diagnostic scores remain unclear.

Present Study

The literature suggests that AIRT and MIRT can improve the reliability of subscores by incorporating collateral information, but these improvements often come at the cost of reduced distinctiveness. At the same time, DCMs have demonstrated considerable promise as diagnostic tools capable of producing accurate classifications and meaningful feedback. However, direct comparisons of DCMs with AIRT and MIRT have been limited, particularly with respect to classification accuracy, distinctiveness, and incremental validity.

To address this gap, the present study compares AIRT, MIRT, and DCM approaches under a variety of testing conditions. Specifically, the study evaluates (a) classification accuracy, (b) subscore distinctiveness, and (c) incremental validity evidence of subscores while manipulating factors known to influence subscore quality, including subscale length, item difficulty distribution, and inter-subdomain correlations.

The findings will extend existing evidence regarding the reliability, distinctiveness, and validity of DCM-based diagnostic information relative to that provided by AIRT and MIRT approaches. By clarifying the conditions under which each method performs most effectively, this study will inform the selection of diagnostic methods that are appropriate for the intended use of test scores. Ultimately, the results may contribute to more accurate diagnostic decisions and more effective instructional interventions to support student learning.

METHODS

Simulation Design

A Monte Carlo simulation study was conducted to compare AIRT, MIRT, and DCM approaches with respect to classification accuracy, subscore distinctiveness, and incremental validity. Overall ability estimates from a unidimensional IRT (UIRT) model served as the reference for evaluating the distinctiveness and incremental validity of diagnostic subscores.

The simulation employed a fully crossed design manipulating three factors that have been shown to influence subscore quality: subscale length, item difficulty distribution, and inter-subdomain correlation. Subscale length was varied at four levels (5, 10, 20, and 30 items per subscale). Item difficulty distributions included a baseline condition, a high-variance condition, and a high-mean condition. Inter-subdomain correlations were manipulated at four levels (.30, .50, .70, and .80). In addition, criterion validity was varied at two levels ($\rho = .50$ and $.80$) for incremental validity analyses. The assessment measured two subdomains using a simple structure in which each item loaded on only one latent trait. Sample size was fixed at 2,000 examinees per replication.

The fully crossed design yielded 48 simulation conditions. One hundred replications were generated for each condition, resulting in 4,800 simulated data sets. All the manipulated factors are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Manipulated Design Factors

MF	Level
Diagnostic methods (DM)	AIRT MIRT DCM UIRT
Subscale length (L)	5 items per subscale 10 items per subscale 20 items per subscale 30 items per subscale
Distribution of item difficulty (D)	BL: $b \sim N(0, 1)$ HV: $b \sim N(0, 1.5^2)$ HM: $b \sim N(1, 1)$
Inter-subscale correlations (R)	.30 .50 .70 .80
Magnitude of criterion validity coefficients (C)	HCV: 64 % criterion validity LCV: 25 % criterion validity

Note. MF = manipulated factors, AIRT = augmented IRT, MIRT = multidimensional IRT, DCM = diagnostic classification model, UIRT = unidimensional IRT, BL = baseline, HV = high variability, HM = high mean, HCV = high criterion validity, LCV = low criterion validity.

Data Generation

For each replication, person parameters for the two subdomains were generated from a bivariate normal distribution with means of zero, standard deviations of one, and covariances corresponding to the target inter-subdomain correlations. Item discrimination parameters were sampled from empirical estimates obtained from the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) Grade 4 reading assessment. Item difficulty parameters were generated according to the designated difficulty-distribution condition.

Binary item responses were generated using a compensatory two-dimensional two-parameter normal-ogive (2PNO) model. Criterion variables were generated to correlate with the true latent abilities at either .50 or .80, corresponding to low- and high-validity conditions. Criterion scores were constructed to reflect contributions from both subdomains, thereby allowing evaluation of the incremental predictive value of diagnostic subscores.

Score Estimation

Four scoring approaches were evaluated: UIRT, AIRT, MIRT, and DCM. Overall ability estimates were obtained using a unidimensional 2PNO model. AIRT estimates were generated by first estimating subdomain-specific abilities using separate unidimensional IRT models and then augmenting those estimates using collateral information from the alternate subdomain. MIRT estimates were obtained using a two-dimensional 2PNO model that simultaneously estimated both latent traits while accounting for their correlation.

For the DCM approach, attributes were estimated using the additive cognitive diagnostic model (ACDM), a compensatory DCM that models the additive contribution of multiple attributes to item responses. ACDM was selected because its compensatory structure matched the data-generating process and because its relatively

parsimonious parameterization has been shown to support stable estimation compared with more complex diagnostic classification models (Williamson, 2023).

To facilitate equivalent comparisons across diagnostic methods, the present study utilized both binary mastery classifications and continuous proficiency scores. For the IRT approach, continuous ability estimates were dichotomized at $\theta = 0$ to create mastery classifications analogous to those produced by the DCM. Conversely, for the DCM approach, PPMs served as the continuous proficiency scores, thereby providing a counterpart to the continuous ability estimates generated by the IRT-based approaches. IRT-based ability estimates were obtained using maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimation, whereas ACDM attribute estimates were obtained using expected a posteriori (EAP) estimation.

All IRT analyses were conducted using the R package *mirt* (Chalmers, 2012), and DCM analyses were conducted using the R package *GDINA* (Ma & de la Torre, 2020).

Evaluation Criteria

Three aspects of subscore quality were evaluated: classification accuracy, subscore distinctiveness, and incremental validity.

Classification Accuracy

Classification accuracy was evaluated using correct classification rate (CCR), Cohen's (1960) kappa (κ), sensitivity, and specificity. These indices were computed by comparing estimated mastery classifications with true mastery classifications. Because the two subdomains were generated under identical conditions, classification indices were aggregated across subdomains within each replication.

Subscore Distinctiveness

Subscore distinctiveness was evaluated using correlations among subscores and correlations between subscores and overall ability estimates. Pearson correlations were computed for continuous proficiency estimates, whereas tetrachoric correlations were computed for mastery classifications. Lower correlations indicate greater distinctiveness of subscores from one another and from the overall score.

Incremental Validity

Incremental validity was evaluated using hierarchical regression analyses. In the first model (M_1), overall ability estimates from the UIRT model were used to predict the continuous criterion variable. In the second model (M_2), diagnostic subscores, operationalized as continuous proficiency scores, were added as predictors. Incremental validity was quantified by the increase in adjusted R^2 attributable to the subscores beyond the overall score.

Data Analysis

Convergence rates and model fit were first examined to evaluate the practical feasibility of each estimation method. Model fit was assessed using the standardized root mean square residual (*SRMSR*), Akaike information criterion (*AIC*), and Bayesian information criterion (*BIC*).

To examine the effects of simulation conditions on classification accuracy and incremental validity, mixed analyses of variance (*ANOVAs*) were conducted with diagnostic method as a within-subject factor and subscale length, item difficulty distribution, and inter-subdomain correlation as between-subject factors. Significant effects were followed by Bonferroni-adjusted post hoc comparisons. Effect sizes were evaluated using generalized eta squared (η_G^2) (Olejnik & Algina, 2003), with values of .06 or greater interpreted as practically meaningful.

RESULTS

Preliminary Analyses

Convergence rates were high across all estimation methods. ACDM converged successfully in all 4,800 replications, whereas MIRT, UIRT, and AIRT failed to converge in only 1, 7, and 12 replications, respectively. Consequently, only 15 replications (< 0.5%) were excluded from subsequent analyses.

Model-fit indices generally favored the IRT-based approaches. Across conditions, MIRT yielded the lowest average *AIC* and *BIC* values, followed by AIRT, whereas UIRT and ACDM produced comparable information criteria. Absolute fit was also favorable for MIRT and AIRT, both of which achieved *SRMSR* values below .05 in all replications, whereas ACDM had *SRMSR* values greater than .05 in three replications. Although ACDM exhibited somewhat poorer fit than the generating MIRT model, its fit was generally acceptable across simulation conditions.

Research Question 1: Classification Accuracy

Overall Classification Accuracy

As shown in Table 2, across conditions, AIRT and MIRT produced nearly identical classification performance and consistently outperformed ACDM. Average CCR was .83 for both AIRT and MIRT compared with .82 for ACDM. Similarly, average Cohen's κ values were .65 for AIRT and MIRT and .63 for ACDM.

Subscale length exerted the strongest influence on classification accuracy. Across methods, CCR increased from .75 for 5-item subscales to .88 for 30-item subscales, whereas κ increased from .51 to .75. Item difficulty distribution and inter-subdomain correlation also affected classification performance, although to a lesser extent. Accuracy improved when item difficulty was better aligned with examinee ability and when correlations among subdomains increased.

Table 2

CCR by Manipulated Factors

MF	Level	N	AIRT	MIRT	ACDM
L	5	1199	.76	.76	.75
	10	1197	.81	.81	.80
	20	1192	.86	.86	.85
	30	1197	.88	.88	.87
D	BL	1599	.84	.84	.83
	HV	1587	.82	.82	.82
	HM	1599	.82	.82	.80
R	.30	1196	.82	.82	.81
	.50	1197	.82	.82	.81
	.70	1197	.83	.83	.82
	.80	1195	.84	.84	.83
All		4785	.83	.83	.82

Note. CCR = correct classification rates, MF = manipulated factors, AIRT = augmented IRT, MIRT = multidimensional IRT, ACDM = additive CDM, L = subscale length, D = item difficulty distribution, R = inter-subscore correlations, BL = baseline, HV = high variability, HM = high mean.

Table 3 presents the results of the four-way mixed *ANOVA* on the CCR. The findings revealed significant main effects of diagnostic method, subscale length, item difficulty distribution, and inter-subdomain correlation for both CCR and κ . However, the largest effects were associated with subscale length ($\eta_G^2 = .91$), followed by item difficulty distribution ($\eta_G^2 = .21$) and inter-subdomain correlation ($\eta_G^2 = .18$). The effect of diagnostic method was comparatively smaller ($\eta_G^2 = .12$).

Table 3

Four-Way Mixed ANOVA Results for CCR

Source	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	η_G^2
<u>Within-subjects</u>				
DM	1.07	6744.81	<.001	.12
DM x L	3.22	37.80	<.001	<.001
DM x D	2.15	1626.09	<.001	.06
DM x R	3.22	3.23	<.001	<.001
DM x L x D	6.44	6.07	<.001	<.001
DM x L x R	9.66	3.91	<.001	<.001
DM x D x R	6.44	0.53	.80	<.001
DM x L x D x R	19.32	0.17	>.99	<.001
Error	5085.44			
<u>Between-subjects</u>				
L	3	18133.95	.001	.91
D	2	677.37	<.001	.21
R	3	390.96	<.001	.18
L x D	6	5.27	<.001	.01
L x R	9	22.27	<.001	.04
D x R	6	0.73	.63	<.001
L x D x R	18	0.04	>.99	<.001
Error	4737			

Note. CCR = correct classification rates, η_G^2 = generalized eta squared, DM = diagnostic method, L = subscale length, D = item difficulty distribution, R = inter-subscore correlations.

Sensitivity and Specificity

Although overall classification accuracy differed only modestly across methods, larger differences emerged when sensitivity and specificity were examined separately. Across conditions, AIRT and MIRT yielded nearly identical sensitivity values (both $M = .83$), whereas ACDM produced lower sensitivity ($M = .78$). In contrast, ACDM produced higher specificity ($M = .85$) than either AIRT ($M = .82$) or MIRT ($M = .83$).

These differences were largely attributable to the high-mean difficulty condition, in which items were substantially more difficult than examinee ability. Under this condition, ACDM underestimated mastery rates ($M = .38$) relative to the true mastery rate of .50, whereas AIRT and MIRT maintained accurate mastery estimates (approximately .50). Consequently, ACDM exhibited substantially lower sensitivity (.68) but substantially higher

specificity (.92) than the IRT-based methods. In contrast, differences among methods were negligible under the baseline and high-variability difficulty conditions. Figure 1 illustrates the main and interaction effects of the manipulated factors on average sensitivity and specificity.

Taken together, the results indicate that AIRT and MIRT provided highly similar and generally superior classification performance. Although ACDM produced slightly lower overall classification accuracy, its performance was largely comparable to the IRT-based methods except when item difficulty substantially exceeded examinee ability.

Figure 1
Average Sensitivity and Specificity by Simulation Conditions

Note. AIRT = augmented IRT, MIRT = multidimensional IRT, ACDM = additive CDM, BL = baseline, HV = high variability, HM = high mean.

Research Question 2: Subscore Distinctiveness

Subscore distinctiveness was evaluated using correlations among subscores and correlations between subscores and overall scores. Table 4 summarizes the subscore distinctiveness results for each combination of the manipulated factors. Across methods, inter-subscore correlations increased as the true correlations among subdomains increased and decreased as subscale length increased. Item difficulty distribution had relatively little influence on distinctiveness.

For continuous proficiency estimates, AIRT ($M = .70$) and MIRT ($M = .69$) yielded highly similar inter-subscore correlations, whereas ACDM ($M = .60$) generally produced lower correlations among subscores. Correlations between subscores and overall scores were high for all methods, indicating substantial overlap between domain-specific and overall proficiency estimates. Nevertheless, ACDM subscores tended to be somewhat less strongly associated with overall scores than those obtained from AIRT and MIRT, suggesting greater differentiation from overall proficiency.

This greater distinctiveness may be partly attributable to the restricted range of ACDM proficiency scores, which are bounded between 0 and 1. To examine this possibility, PPMs of ACDM were transformed to the logit scale, $\log[\text{PPM}/(1 - \text{PPM})]$, thereby reducing the effects of range restriction. Following the transformation, the average correlations of ACDM increased somewhat; however, it remained slightly lower than those observed for the IRT-based methods.

Despite these differences, correlations among subscores and between subscores and overall scores remained substantial across all methods. Thus, although ACDM produced somewhat more differentiated diagnostic information, all three approaches yielded subscores that were strongly related to overall proficiency.

Table 4

Inter-Subscore Correlations and Average Correlations between Overall Scores and Two Subscore by Manipulated Factors Using Discrete and Continuous Score Estimates

MF	Level	N	Tetrachoric correlations					
			AIRT	MIRT	ACDM	AIRT-UIRT	MIRT-UIRT	ACDM-UIRT
L	5	1199	.75	.73	.77	.91	.91	.91
	10	1197	.72	.69	.71	.91	.90	.91
	20	1192	.68	.65	.67	.91	.90	.91
	30	1197	.66	.64	.65	.90	.90	.90
D	BL	1599	.70	.67	.69	.91	.90	.91
	HV	1587	.70	.68	.71	.91	.91	.91
	HM	1599	.70	.68	.70	.91	.90	.90
R	.30	1196	.40	.38	.40	.81	.80	.81
	.50	1197	.64	.61	.64	.90	.89	.90
	.70	1197	.84	.82	.84	.96	.95	.95
	.80	1195	.92	.90	.91	.98	.97	.97
All	4785	.70	.68	.70	.91	.90	.91	

MF	Level	N	Pearson correlations					
			AIRT	MIRT	ACDM	AIRT-UIRT	MIRT-UIRT	ACDM-UIRT
L	5	1199	.76	.74	.71 (.73)	.92	.92	.87 (.91)
	10	1197	.72	.70	.63 (.65)	.92	.91	.82 (.89)
	20	1192	.67	.66	.55 (.60)	.91	.91	.79 (.87)
	30	1197	.65	.64	.52 (.57)	.90	.90	.77 (.84)
D	BL	1599	.70	.68	.59 (.63)	.91	.91	.81 (.87)
	HV	1587	.70	.69	.61 (.64)	.91	.91	.81 (.88)
	HM	1599	.71	.69	.60 (.64)	.91	.91	.81 (.88)
R	.30	1196	.40	.39	.32 (.36)	.81	.81	.73 (.79)
	.50	1197	.64	.63	.53 (.58)	.90	.90	.80 (.87)
	.70	1197	.84	.83	.73 (.77)	.96	.95	.85 (.92)
	.80	1195	.92	.91	.82 (.84)	.98	.98	.86 (.93)
All	4785	.70	.69	.60 (.64)	.91	.91	.81 (.88)	

Note. MF = manipulated factors, AIRT = augmented IRT, MIRT = multidimensional IRT, ACDM = additive CDM, L = subscale length, D = item difficulty distribution, R = inter-subscore correlations, BL = baseline, HV = high variability, HM = high mean. AIRT-UIRT, MIRT-UIRT, and ACDM-UIRT refer to average correlations

between overall scores and two subscores of AIRT, MIRT, and ACDM, respectively. Correlations using logit transformed proficiency scores of ACDM appear inside the parentheses.

Research Question 3: Incremental Validity

Incremental validity was evaluated as the increase in explained variance obtained by adding diagnostic subscores to a prediction model that already included an overall score. Table 5 presents the R^2 values for the restricted (M_1) and full (M_2) regression models by manipulated factors. Across conditions, all three diagnostic approaches yielded similar levels of criterion-related validity. Models containing both overall scores and subscores explained slightly more variance in the criterion than models based solely on overall scores.

Under the high-validity condition, full models explained approximately 55% of the variance in the criterion, whereas models containing only the overall score explained approximately 54%. The resulting increase in explained variance attributable to diagnostic subscores was small, averaging approximately .008 for AIRT and MIRT and .006 for ACDM. Similar patterns emerged under the low-validity condition, although overall levels of explained variance were lower.

Table 5

R² for Restricted versus Full Regression Models by Manipulated Factors

MF	Level	N	M ₁		M ₂					
			UIRT		AIRT		MIRT		ACDM	
			HCV	LCV	HCV	LCV	HCV	LCV	HCV	LCV
L	5	1199	.40	.19	.41	.19	.41	.19	.41	.19
	10	1197	.52	.24	.53	.25	.53	.25	.53	.25
	20	1192	.61	.29	.62	.29	.62	.29	.61	.29
	30	1197	.64	.30	.65	.30	.65	.30	.65	.30
D	BL	1599	.56	.26	.56	.26	.56	.26	.56	.26
	HV	1587	.54	.25	.55	.26	.55	.26	.54	.25
	HM	1599	.54	.25	.54	.25	.54	.25	.54	.25
R	.30	1196	.48	.21	.50	.22	.50	.22	.50	.21
	.50	1197	.53	.24	.54	.25	.54	.25	.54	.25
	.70	1197	.57	.28	.57	.28	.57	.28	.57	.28
	.80	1195	.59	.29	.59	.29	.59	.29	.59	.29
All		4785	.54	.25	.55	.26	.55	.26	.55	.26

Note. MF = manipulated factors, M₁ = restricted regression model with overall scores as the only predictor, M₂ = full regression model with two subscores plus overall scores as predictors, UIRT = unidimensional IRT, AIRT = augmented IRT, MIRT = multidimensional IRT, ACDM = additive CDM, HCV = high criterion validity, LCV = low criterion validity, L = subscale length, D = item difficulty distribution, R = inter-subscore correlations, BL = baseline, HV = high variability, HM = high mean. Numbers inside parentheses indicate the difference in adjusted R^2 between full and restricted models for the given diagnostic method.

The four-way mixed ANOVA results for R^2 (Table 6) indicated that incremental validity was influenced primarily by subscale length and inter-subdomain correlations. The contribution of subscores beyond the overall score increased as subdomains became less correlated and as subscales became longer. Differences among diagnostic

methods were comparatively small. Although AIRT and MIRT generally produced slightly larger increases in explained variance than ACDM, the practical magnitude of these differences was minimal.

Table 6

Four-Way Mixed ANOVA Results for R²

Source	df	HCV			LCV			
		F	p	η_G^2	df	F	p	η_G^2
<u>Within-subjects</u>								
DM	1.06	2912.32	<.001	.02	1.21	2188.39	<.001	.01
DM x L	3.19	122.70	<.001	.00	3.63	84.97	<.001	<.001
DM x D	2.12	1.29	.28	<.001	2.42	0.46	.67	<.001
DM x R	3.19	1178.17	<.001	.02	3.63	845.41	<.001	.01
DM x L x D	6.37	1.03	.41	<.001	7.26	0.84	.56	<.001
DM x L x R	9.56	45.39	<.001	<.001	10.89	31.68	<.001	<.001
DM x D x R	6.37	0.48	.84	<.001	7.26	0.23	.98	<.001
DM x L x D x R	19.12	0.48	.97	<.001	21.77	0.42	.99	<.001
Error	5032.20				5730.22			
<u>Between-subjects</u>								
L	3	21110.70	<.001	.93	3	8800.79	<.001	.85
D	2	279.27	<.001	.10	2	130.73	<.001	.05
R	3	3229.92	<.001	.67	3	3816.98	<.001	.71
L x D	6	8.75	<.001	.01	6	5.90	<.001	.01
L x R	9	5.92	<.001	.01	9	2.12	.03	<.001
D x R	6	0.08	>.999	<.001	6	0.33	.92	<.001
L x D x R	18	0.05	>.999	<.001	18	0.07	>.999	<.001
Error	4737				4737			

Note. HCV = high criterion validity, LCV = low criterion validity, η_G^2 = generalized eta squared, DM = diagnostic method, L = subscale length, D = item difficulty distribution, R = inter-subscore correlations.

Overall, the results indicate that diagnostic subscores provided statistically detectable but modest incremental validity beyond overall scores. Thus, improvements in reliability achieved through diagnostic scoring methods did not translate into substantial gains in predictive utility.

Summary of Findings

Across the three research questions, AIRT and MIRT consistently produced nearly identical results and generally outperformed ACDM in classification accuracy. ACDM, however, yielded somewhat more distinct subscores and stronger separation from overall proficiency. With respect to incremental validity, all three approaches provided only modest gains beyond overall scores. More importantly, simulation conditions—subscale length, item

difficulty distribution, and inter-subdomain correlation—had substantially larger effects on subscore quality than the choice of diagnostic method itself.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to compare AIRT, MIRT, and DCM approaches with respect to classification accuracy, subscore distinctiveness, and incremental validity. Although these approaches are frequently used to support diagnostic score reporting, relatively little research has directly compared their psychometric properties under common testing conditions. Overall, the findings suggest that differences among diagnostic methods were modest relative to the effects of test design characteristics, particularly subscale length, item difficulty distribution, and inter-subdomain correlations.

Classification Accuracy

AIRT and MIRT produced nearly identical classification accuracy across conditions and generally outperformed ACDM. However, differences among methods were small when item difficulty was aligned with examinee ability and cut scores. The largest discrepancies emerged when items were substantially more difficult than examinee ability. Under these conditions, ACDM underestimated mastery rates, resulting in lower sensitivity but higher specificity than the IRT-based approaches.

These findings suggest that DCM classifications may be more sensitive to model–data misfit than classifications obtained from IRT-based methods. Because the data in the present study were generated from an IRT model, the poorer performance of ACDM under extreme difficulty conditions is not entirely surprising. Nevertheless, the results highlight an important practical consideration: when DCMs are applied to assessments originally developed within an IRT framework, additional calibration, linking, or standard-setting procedures may be necessary to support stable criterion-referenced interpretations.

More importantly, classification accuracy was driven primarily by assessment characteristics rather than by the choice of diagnostic method. Longer subscales, better alignment between item difficulty and examinee ability, and stronger inter-subdomain correlations consistently improved classification accuracy across all methods. These findings reinforce previous research demonstrating that test design remains a critical determinant of score quality regardless of the estimation framework employed.

Subscore Distinctiveness

A second objective was to examine the extent to which subscores provided information distinct from other subscores and from overall proficiency. Across methods, subscore distinctiveness was strongly influenced by subscale length and inter-subdomain correlations. Distinctiveness increased as subscales became longer and as correlations among subdomains decreased.

Among the methods examined, ACDM produced somewhat more distinct subscores than AIRT and MIRT when continuous proficiency estimates were considered. This finding is consistent with the theoretical foundations of DCMs, which are designed to classify examinees with respect to discrete attributes rather than estimate positions along continuous latent dimensions. In contrast, AIRT and MIRT improve subscore precision by borrowing information from related dimensions, a process that necessarily increases the similarity among subscores.

Despite these differences, correlations among subscores and between subscores and overall scores remained substantial across all methods. Thus, while DCMs yielded somewhat greater differentiation among subscores, the practical distinction between overall and domain-specific information remained limited under many conditions.

Incremental Validity

The third objective was to evaluate whether diagnostic subscores contributed information beyond that provided by an overall score. Across all conditions, subscores explained only a small amount of additional variance in the criterion after controlling for overall proficiency. Although these increments were statistically detectable, their practical magnitude was modest regardless of the estimation method used.

The strongest determinant of incremental validity was subscore distinctiveness. As inter-subdomain correlations increased, the unique contribution of subscores declined rapidly. This finding is consistent with previous research suggesting that the added value of subscores depends largely on their ability to capture information that is not already reflected in the overall score. When subdomains are highly correlated, overall scores already summarize much of the information contained in individual subscores, leaving little opportunity for additional predictive value.

Notably, AIRT, MIRT, and ACDM yielded remarkably similar levels of incremental validity despite differences in classification accuracy and distinctiveness. This result suggests that improvements in subscore reliability do not necessarily translate into meaningful gains in predictive utility. Consequently, decisions regarding diagnostic score reporting should consider not only reliability but also whether subscores provide information that is sufficiently distinct to justify separate interpretation.

Implications for Diagnostic Score Reporting

Taken together, the findings suggest that the practical utility of diagnostic scores depends more on assessment design than on the specific estimation method employed. Longer subscales and clearer differentiation among subdomains consistently improved the quality of diagnostic information, whereas differences among AIRT, MIRT, and ACDM were comparatively modest.

From a score-reporting perspective, these results caution against assuming that statistically enhanced subscores necessarily provide meaningful added value. Although AIRT and MIRT improved classification accuracy, and ACDM yielded somewhat more differentiated subscores, all methods produced limited incremental validity beyond overall scores. Therefore, reporting subscores may be most defensible when assessments are explicitly designed to measure distinct domains with adequate numbers of items rather than when subscores are retrofitted from largely unidimensional assessments.

Limitations and Future Directions

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, as with any simulation study, the results are limited to the conditions examined. Different combinations of sample size, attribute structure, Q-matrix specification, or model complexity may yield different results. Second, data were generated using a multidimensional IRT model. Although this design reflects many operational testing situations, it may place DCMs at a relative disadvantage because the generating model differs from the estimation model. Future studies should compare diagnostic methods under both IRT- and DCM-generated data. Third, the present study evaluated incremental validity using continuous proficiency estimates. When the focus of a study is to evaluate the added value of subscores for classification purposes, researchers may consider the procedure proposed by Sinharay (2014). Similar to the added-value analysis proposed by Haberman (2008), Sinharay's procedure evaluates whether classifications based on observed subscores more accurately predict classifications based on true subscores than do classifications based on observed total scores. Fourth, the present study focused on a limited set of external criteria and did not investigate potential subgroup differences. Future research should examine whether the relative utility of diagnostic methods varies across different types of external criteria and across subgroups of examinees. Finally, because the study focused on simple test structures, additional research is needed to evaluate diagnostic methods in assessments that incorporate more complex multidimensional structures (i.e., three- or higher-dimensional) and cognitive models (i.e., noncompensatory or nonadditive DCMs).

Conclusion

This study provides one of the few direct comparisons of AIRT, MIRT, and DCM approaches with respect to classification accuracy, subscore distinctiveness, and incremental validity. Overall, AIRT and MIRT produced nearly identical results and generally yielded higher classification accuracy than ACDM, whereas ACDM produced somewhat more distinct subscores. However, differences among methods were relatively small compared with the influence of test design characteristics. Across all approaches, the incremental validity of subscores beyond overall scores was modest. These findings suggest that the value of diagnostic score reporting depends less on the estimation framework and more on the extent to which assessments are designed to support reliable and distinct measurement of multiple domains.

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